

THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PREPOSITIONS IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article explores the similarities and differences in the usage of prepositions in English and Russian. It examines the forms, functions, and grammatical nuances of prepositions in both languages, highlighting key challenges faced by learners. While English prepositions are invariant and often idiomatic, Russian prepositions are intricately linked to the case system, requiring a deeper understanding of grammatical structures. By providing a detailed comparison, the article aims to facilitate a better grasp of prepositional usage for language learners and linguists alike.

Keywords: prepositions, English language, Russian language, case system, grammatical comparison, language learning, linguistic analysis

Introduction

To begin with, prepositions in English and Russian share a common purpose: to link nouns, pronouns, or phrases to other words within a sentence. However, the way they function and the rules governing their usage differ significantly between the two languages. Understanding these differences is essential for learners aiming to achieve fluency in either language.

Firstly, English prepositions are generally invariant in form. Words like "in," "on," "at," "with," and "by" remain unchanged regardless of the context. For example:

- She is **in** the room.
- The book is **on** the table [3, 408-427].

In contrast, Russian prepositions often interact with the case system, meaning their usage depends on the grammatical case of the associated noun or pronoun. For example, the preposition "в" (in) requires the accusative case to indicate direction and the prepositional case to indicate location:

- Она в комнату (в + accusative = into the room).
- Она в комнате (в + prepositional = in the room).

Moving forward, the way prepositions convey meaning often varies between the two languages. In English, prepositions tend to have fixed meanings and are used in relatively predictable patterns. For instance:

- He arrived **at** the station.

- She is good at math.

In Russian, the meaning of prepositions can be more flexible and context-dependent. The same preposition can have multiple meanings based on the case it governs. For example, the preposition "на" can indicate location (на + prepositional = on/in) or direction (на + accusative = onto):

- Книга на столе (на + prepositional = the book is on the table).
- Положите книгу на стол (на + accusative = put the book onto the table).

Another key point to consider is the challenge prepositions present to learners of both languages. For English learners, prepositions are often a source of confusion because they do not follow strict logical rules. For example:

- She is **interested in** science.
- He is **good at** sports [1, 9-23].

The choice of preposition may appear arbitrary and must often be memorized.

On the other hand, learners of Russian must contend with the complexity of the case system. Not only must they remember the correct preposition, but they must also know how it interacts with the noun's case. For instance:

- Она ходит в школу (в + accusative = she goes to school).
- Она в школе (в + prepositional = she is at school).

Moreover, linking words such as "similarly," "however," and "in contrast" help to draw parallels and distinctions between the two languages. For example:

- **Similarly**, both languages use prepositions to indicate relationships between words.
- **However**, English prepositions are not influenced by grammatical cases, unlike Russian.
- **In contrast**, Russian prepositions often require detailed knowledge of the case system.

Conclusion

To conclude, while English and Russian prepositions serve the same fundamental purpose, their forms and usage are governed by distinct linguistic principles. English prepositions are simpler in form but can be idiomatic and unpredictable. Russian prepositions, on the other hand, are deeply intertwined with the case system, adding complexity but also precision to the language. By understanding these differences, learners can better navigate the challenges of mastering prepositions in either language.

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